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Research on breast cancer induced chronic conditions
supported by causal analysis of multi-source data

D7.4 – Best practices for integration of multi-source RWD into existing clinical workflows

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Table of Contents

Document History	3
Abbreviations and Acronyms.....	5
Executive Summary.....	6
1 Introduction.....	7
1.1 Aim.....	8
1.2 Intended audience	8
1.3 Project partners and acronyms.....	8
1.4 Methodology	9
1.5 Organization of the document	9
2 Integration of patient-driven feature into the pApp.....	10
2.1 Background.....	10
2.2 Co-Creation as a design principle.....	11
2.3 Identification of the need.....	12
2.4 Development process.....	13
3 Development of a unified advisory guide for personalized consultations with BCP 15	
3.1 Background and rationale.....	15
3.2 Development process.....	17
3.3 Structure and content of the guide	18
Conclusions.....	23
References	24
Annex	25
A. ANNEX A: Advisory lifestyle guidelines	26
B. ANNEX B: Positive annotation categories	51

Abbreviations and Acronyms

BCP	Breast Cancer Patient
BCS	Breast Cancer Survivor
CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
HCP	Health Care Professional
KI	Karolinska Institutet
pApp	REBECCA's Patient App
PROM	Patient-Reported Outcome Measures
QoL	Quality of Life
RWD	Real-World Data
WCRF	World Cancer Research Fund
WHO	World Health Organization

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the methodology and outcomes of co-creation and evidence synthesis activities conducted within the REBECCA project to support the integration of multi-source real-world data (RWD) into clinical workflows for breast cancer patient management. The REBECCA project, which was implemented between April 2021 and September 2025, aimed to leverage RWD collected from the patient application (pApp), smartphones, smartwatches, and patient-reported outcomes to complement traditional clinical research and enhance understanding of lifestyle, emotional well-being, and quality of life in breast cancer patients and survivors. The pApp is a mobile application for RWD collection that combines wearable connectivity, photo logging, short questionnaires, and GPS-based mobility tracking.

A structured co-creation approach ensured that the digital tools developed were both clinically relevant and meaningful to patients. Breast cancer patients (BPCs), healthcare professionals (HCPs), and researchers from Sweden, Spain, and Norway actively participated in workshops, focus groups and validation sessions to enhance the integration of real-world data into existing clinical workflows. These collaborative efforts contributed to several improvements to the system and its usage. In this deliverable, we focus on two examples from the REBECCA project and analyse them as good practices for integrating RWD: the addition of the “Life Events” feature in the pApp and the creation of a unified advisory guide for HCPs.

Specifically, in response to patient feedback, the “Life Events” feature was introduced in the pApp, replacing the original “environment stressor” annotation category. This change enabled patients to record both positive and negative daily experiences, offering a more balanced and comprehensive view of their life. Furthermore, to ensure consistent implementation of the REBECCA-assisted lifestyle consultations across the clinical sites, Karolinska Institutet developed a comprehensive advisory guide to support personalized lifestyle consultations. Drawing on international guidelines and adapting them to the REBECCA context, the guide was organized across six lifestyle domains plus an additional category of REBECCA-specific indicators, including mobility, work status, eating behaviours, and social support. The guide provided coded recommendations and practical examples to facilitate consistent, structured consultations by the HCPs across all clinical sites. The guide is publicly available as a standalone document on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17425256>.

Together, the enhanced reporting through the pApp and the development of the advisory guide for HCPs exemplify best practices for integrating patient-generated data into clinical workflows.

1 Introduction

Breast cancer stands as the most prevalent cancer among women globally, representing the second-highest number of yearly incidences (approximately 11.6% of global new cancer cases in 2018³), contributing to one-fifth of overall global cancer mortality. In Europe alone, breast cancer emerges as the most frequently diagnosed cancer annually, with approximately 523,000 new cases reported in 2018.⁴ Breast cancer patients (BCPs) constitute the largest subgroup within the expanding community of cancer patients worldwide.⁵ Beyond primary cancer treatment, which increasingly yields success, breast cancer survivors (BCSs) grapple with substantial life challenges. These challenges encompass the management of medical conditions, adjustments in lifestyle resulting from cancer and its treatment, intense fear of cancer recurrence,⁶ and difficulties in resuming personal and professional responsibilities. These challenges often lead to additional long-term financial burdens.⁷ Surviving breast cancer becomes a transformative event, becoming the focal point in a multi-faceted framework of health dependencies that significantly impact the patients' Quality of Life (QoL), mental/emotional state, and overall lifestyle.⁸

REBECCA aims to harness the potential of "*real-world data*" (RWD) – including clinical data, patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs), and data collected from smartphones and smartwatches, along with episodic patient reports – to support clinical research on complex chronic conditions as a complementary approach to randomized controlled trials, and to improve clinical workflows through personalised follow-ups. Going beyond traditional research and clinical data analysis, REBECCA collaborated with AMAZONA, the largest Swedish breast cancer association and a member of the REBECCA consortium. AMAZONA's input through the co-creation activities played a key role in shaping the REBECCA system, which facilitates detailed monitoring of data from clinical resources, multiple wearables, online behaviour, and registry data (the "REBECCA 360°" monitoring). This comprehensive approach allows for the monitoring of patients' physical, physiological, emotional, and QoL trajectories.

³ Global Cancer Observatory. <https://gco.iarc.fr/>

⁴ Ferlay et al. Cancer incidence and mortality in Europe: estimates for 40 countries and 25 major cancers in 2018. *Eur J Cancer* (2018)

⁵ American Cancer Society (2016). Cancer Treatment and Survivorship Facts and Figures. Online: <https://tinyurl.com/yaugv727>

⁶ Ellegaard et al. Fear of cancer recurrence and unmet needs among breast cancer survivors in the first five years. *Acta Oncologica* 56.2 (2017):314

⁷ Fenn et al. Impact of financial burden of cancer on survivors' quality of life. *J Oncol Pract* 10.5 (2014):332

⁸ Koch et al. Quality of life in long-term breast cancer survivors, 10-year longitudinal population-based study. *Acta Oncol* 52.6 (2013): 1119

The project commenced in April 2021 and finished in September 2025, holding the potential to generate new insights into the clinical management of cancer patients and potentially shaping future breast cancer rehabilitation guidelines. Best practices derived from the REBECCA studies will be disseminated to researchers, public health entities, and regulatory bodies across Europe, fostering the broader adoption of RWD in clinical research. Furthermore, the REBECCA platform, equipped for detailed monitoring and privacy-preserving federated cross-country data analysis, will serve as an infrastructure for ongoing advancements in RWD usage beyond the project's conclusion. Through these endeavours, REBECCA aims to encourage the widespread adoption of RWD for comprehending chronic health conditions, ultimately establishing it as a valuable tool in clinical research and patient management.

1.1 Aim

The aim of this deliverable is to describe the co-creation activities and evidence synthesis processes conducted within the REBECCA project to support the integration of multi-source RWD into existing clinical workflows. These activities focused on the introduction of the "Life event" feature in the pApp and the development of the advisory guide to facilitate the use of RWD by healthcare professionals (HCPs) in improving patient management and QoL.

1.2 Intended audience

This public deliverable is intended for HCPs and managers, clinical researchers, policy makers, regulators, patient organisations, and other relevant stakeholders interested in novel digital monitoring tools such as the REBECCA 360°. It is particularly relevant for those involved in breast cancer care and the management of complex chronic conditions, as it provides a methodology for integrating multimodal real-world data into clinical workflows. The document also aims to inform stakeholders about co-creation practices involving patients as the end-users.

1.3 Project partners and acronyms

Throughout this deliverable, the following acronyms are used to refer to REBECCA consortium partners.

Acronym	Partner name	Country
AMAZONA	BROSTCANCERFORENINGEN AMAZONA I STOCKHOLMS LAN	Sweden
INCLIVA	FUNDACION PARA LA INVESTIGACION DEL HOSPITAL CLINICO DE LA COMUNITAT VALENCIANA, FUNDACION INCLIVA	Spain
KI	KAROLINSKA INSTITUTET	Sweden
SUH	HELSE STAVANGER HF	Norway

1.4 Methodology

For the integration of patient-driven features into the pApp, a co-creation approach was applied. Patients, clinicians, and researchers participated in workshops and validation sessions to refine app features and ensure their relevance for both patients and clinical use. This process led to the development of the “Life Events” feature, which allows patients to report both positive and negative daily experiences, improving engagement with the pApp as well as the quality and balance of the RWD collected.

For the development of the unified advisory guide, KI conducted a literature review of international guidelines from authoritative sources (e.g., WHO, WCRF, CDC) to identify evidence-based recommendations relevant to breast cancer survivorship. These were adapted to the REBECCA context and organized across six lifestyle domains – diet, physical activity, sleep, alcohol use, tobacco use, and anxiety/distress – along with REBECCA-specific indicators. The resulting guide was reviewed and validated by consortium partners to ensure consistency across clinical sites.

1.5 Organization of the document

The rest of the document is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the patient-driven development of the pApp feature “Life Events” and Section 3 presents the process of creating the advisory guide for personalized consultations. Annex A includes the advisory lifestyle guidelines. Annex B provides the list of categories proposed as life events (initial, grouped for discussion, and finalised after co-creation), as well as the minutes from the co-creation activities.

2 Integration of patient-driven feature into the pApp

2.1 Background

The pApp is an application built by the REBECCA consortium, with Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece, leading its development, and consists of four different components for data collection:

1. **A picture-taking** feature, which incorporates simple annotations based on the type of picture taken (food/drink and environment stressors) (Figure 1). The food annotations were inspired by the UK's recommendations for a better diet for cancer patients⁹.
2. **A short self-reported questionnaire**, which differs based on the focus of each clinical study (osteoporosis for INCLIVA/Spain, fatigue for SUH/Norway).
3. **GPS data capture**, which records the users' GPS location, allowing for the automatic estimation of their lifestyle mobility (e.g., time at home vs. time outside, radius of gyration, preferred transportation).
4. **Garmin® wearable integration**, using the Garmin Health Standard SDK¹⁰ for capturing behavioural and physiological parameters (e.g., steps, calories, sleep, stress, heart rate).

⁹ Cancer Research UK [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2025 September 29]. What is a healthy diet? Available from: <https://www.cancerresearchuk.org/about-cancer/causes-of-cancer/diet-and-cancer/what-is-a-healthy-diet>

¹⁰ <https://developer.garmin.com/health-sdk/overview/>

Figure 1. Example of the picture taking feature of the pApp.

2.2 Co-Creation as a design principle

A central principle of the REBECCA project was the active involvement of patients in shaping the design and functionality of the pApp. Rather than approaching patients as data providers only, the project placed them at the core of the development process, ensuring that their perspectives, needs, and experiences guided both data collection and interpretation. To achieve this, the project implemented a structured co-creation methodology that engaged patients, HCPs, and researchers in a collaborative process. Through workshops, focus groups, and surveys, patients were able to communicate their needs and preferences, while medical experts and researchers ensured that the collected data retained clinical and scientific relevance.

This iterative process allowed for continuous refinement of the pApp, resulting in a system that was both meaningful for patients and valuable for clinical practice. A clear example of this co-creation in practice was the integration of the “Life events” feature in the annotation categories of the pApp, replacing the initially included “environment stressors” category (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Change of the picture annotation category from “Environment stressor” to the “Life events” feature.

2.3 Identification of the need

Through the initial studies conducted within the REBECCA project, it became clear that BCPs perceived the early design of the annotation category “environment stressor” in the pApp as primarily focused on negative aspects of life. The self-reporting “environment stressor” feature was documenting only negative experiences of life such as inadequate public facilities, unpleasant smells, reduced safety, or weather-related issues that could induce stress in BCP daily lives.

One of the first groups to highlight this as an issue were members of AMAZONA, through a validation study with BCSs conducted in Stockholm in June 2023. AMAZONA is the oldest and largest local breast cancer association in Stockholm County, has approximately 2,000 members and is supported by around 80 volunteers. The non-profit association works to support patients and advocate for their perspectives in healthcare and collaborated with KI in the REBECCA project.

Following the validation study, BCPs and BCSs from AMAZONA provided feedback highlighting that such a narrow focus risked portraying life after cancer as a succession

of difficulties. They emphasised that many BCSs actively try to regain balance, enjoy everyday activities, and cultivate resilience, and that these positive aspects should also be captured. This perspective was later independently confirmed through patient-focused discussions conducted at INCLIVA (Valencia, Spain) and at SUH (Stavanger, Norway). These discussions verified that the desire to capture positive experiences alongside challenges was consistently expressed by BCSs and BCPs across all participating countries (Sweden, Spain, and Norway), indicating that this need was independent of local, cultural, or healthcare system differences.

2.4 Development process

Building on this feedback, KI initiated a structured development process to identify and define “positive events” in the daily lives of BCPs and BCSs that could be reported via the pApp. In September 2023, KI conducted brainstorming sessions with ten women from their research group, inviting them to share experiences and activities that contribute to their well-being. Researchers were also asked to try to provide input to complement the patient perspectives, ensuring that the resulting framework would be meaningful for both patients and clinical practice.

The initial collection of suggestions (Annex B.1) was then categorised into broader domains such as social interactions, hobbies, new experiences, and simple daily pleasures including nature and wellness (Annex B.2) to facilitate organisation and reporting within the pApp. This preliminary categorisation was shared with consortium partners to ensure alignment with scientific and clinical objectives and to confirm that the approach resonated with the broader health research community.

In October 2023, the refined list was presented and discussed in two comprehensive meetings with patient representatives from Amazona. These discussions allowed for final validation of the categories and ensured that the system accurately reflected the lived experiences and expectations of BCPs and BCSs. During these meetings, a key insight emerged: patients’ experiences are dynamic, and what may bring joy on one day could be perceived as stressful on another. Recognising this, the development team decided to introduce a flexible “Life Events” feature within the pApp.

Figure 3. Process of creating positive reporting categories into the pApp.

The “**Life Events**” feature allowed users to report **both positive and negative** daily experiences. Patients could capture these events through pictures and select from the same curated categories, such as social contacts, nature, health, wellness, etc., indicating if the experience was positive or negative for them at that specific moment (Figure 4).

Life events annotation categories

Figure 4. Life event annotation categories

This feature enabled a more balanced view of their daily life but also empowered them to actively participate in documenting their experiences, promoting engagement and self-reflection.

3 Development of a unified advisory guide for personalized consultations with BCPs

3.1 Background and rationale

Within the REBECCA clinical studies at SUH and INCLIVA, the intervention refers to the period after the patient has completed their primary treatment (e.g., first-line chemo- or radiotherapy). These clinical studies included an intervention group that followed standard care enhanced with REBECCA-assisted interventions, and a control group that followed standard care.

In the intervention (REBECCA-assisted) arm, the REBECCA system was integrated into existing patient follow-up routines at the hospitals, enabling clinicians to continuously monitor progress and personalise clinical management. Specifically, HCPs were supported in scheduling patient consultations based on system-predicted declines in functionality, emotional state, or treatment adherence, allowing for just-in-time support to enhance treatment satisfaction and efficacy. During the study period, the experimental group received three REBECCA-assisted lifestyle consultation sessions by an HCP tailored to their individual needs (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Design of the REBECCA clinical studies that were performed in Stavanger (SUH) and Valencia (INCLIVA).

These REBECCA-assisted lifestyle consultations were informed by RWD collected through the REBECCA system (mobile app, smartwatch, and web browser plugin), capturing behavioural, physiological, and emotional health indicators (Figure 6).

Smartphones & REBECCA mobile app

The personal smartphone device of each participant (and their companion if they have) acts as:

- a)** The equipment hub for the connection of the REBECCA smartwatches, locally collecting the generated data through Bluetooth technology.
- b)** A data collection tool itself, used for collection of IMU sensor data (i.e., accelerometer and gyroscope) and geolocation data.
- c)** The means of subjective data collection from the participant (and their companion if they have), with repeated, episodic questions being communicated and answered through the smartphone device.

Daily reminders were sent to prompt them to complete the questionnaire.

- d)** The means of photograph taking (meal/drink pictures & life events).

Instructed to capture and annotate a minimum of three pictures of meals and/or drinks per day, along with a minimum of five life events per week.

- e)** A tool to collect the online behaviour of the participants.

Smartwatches

The chosen device for data collection is the GARMIN Venu Sq or Vivo smart 4; and will be employed to gather continuous sensory data, including accelerometry, gyroscope, sleep, stress, calories burned and heart rate information.

During the intervention, the BCP were asked to wear the wearable:

- In the dominant hand.
- At least 6 days per week, including one weekend day.
- At least 10 hours of wake-up time.
- Sleep with the device on for at least 3 full nights per week of use.

Internet history

Online activity (historical information on key search words, visited website, reaction to posts, participation in online groups, and bookmarked websites)

Figure 6. The data collection devices used in REBECCA studies.

To ensure consistent implementation of the REBECCA-assisted lifestyle consultations across the participating clinical sites, a common reference framework was required. This framework would provide harmonized guidance in line with both international standards and local clinical practice, while at the same time supporting HCPs in their day-to-day work. Importantly, it would also establish a standardized approach for documenting what had been delivered during the consultations, ensuring comparability across sites. In response to this need, KI developed a comprehensive advisory guide, designed to serve as a practical tool and a training resource for the HCP.

3.2 Development process

In May 2023, KI carried out an extensive literature review to identify and synthesize best practices in post-cancer lifestyle guidance. The review drew on authoritative international sources, including the World Health Organization (WHO),¹¹ the World Cancer Research Fund (WCRF),¹² and the Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC).¹³ Where breast cancer-specific recommendations were available, these were prioritized. In cases where no breast cancer-focused material was identified; general population guidelines were reviewed and adapted to the REBECCA context.

Figure 7. Resources for the advisory guide.

The evidence collected was then systematically organized across six lifestyle domains known to influence the health outcomes and QoL of BCP and BCS: diet, physical activity, sleep, alcohol use, tobacco use, and anxiety and distress. In addition to these six lifestyle domains, an additional category for **REBECCA-specific indicators** was introduced. This category included dimensions such as daily mobility, work after

¹¹ <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/physical-activity>

¹² <https://www.wcrf.org/research-policy/evidence-for-our-recommendations/after-a-cancer-diagnosis-follow-recommendations/>

¹³ https://www.cdc.gov/cancer-survivors/healthy-living-guides/sleep.html?CDC_AAref_Val=https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/survivors/healthy-living-guides/physical-health/sleep.htm

treatment, social relationships and support networks, and eating behaviours (e.g., eating rate and portion size).

The outcome of the process described above was a comprehensive, coded document that brought together international and national guidelines and adapted them to the REBECCA context. The guide provides HCPs with clear, domain-specific recommendations and practical examples on how to engage BCPs in constructive discussions about lifestyle topics, such as physical activity or diet, in a supportive way. To facilitate consistency across sites, the guide adopted a standardized reporting format and incorporated coded guidelines, allowing HCPs to document consultations in a uniform manner.

Figure 8. Development process of the advisory guide.

3.3 Structure and content of the guide

The final guide was a 27-page PDF divided into seven sections (six lifestyle domains identified via the literature review plus one section for the REBECCA specific indicators):

1. Guidelines and Advice on **Diet** for BCS
2. Guidelines and Advice on **Physical Activity** for BCS
3. Guidelines and Advice on **Sleep** for BCS
4. Guidelines and Advice on **Alcohol** Use for BCS

5. Guidelines and Advice on **Tobacco** Use for BCS
6. Guidelines and Advice on **Anxiety and Distress** for BCS
7. **REBECCA-specific indicators** for BCS

Figure 9. Advisory Guidelines.

Each section of the guide consisted of two parts. The first part listed the guidelines with their codes and references (e.g. D1, D2, and so forth for dietary recommendations) (Figure 10).

A. Guidelines and Advice on Diet for Breast Cancer Survivors

Guidelines for cancer survivors	
D1	Increased intake of wholegrains and legumes
D2	Increased intake of vegetables and fruits
D3	Limitation of consumption of "fast food" and other processed foods high in fat, starch, or sugars
D4	Limitation of consumption of red meats (maximum 3 portions of 140g cooked red meat/week) and avoid processed meats
D5	Avoidance of sugary drink consumption
Limited evidence for breast cancer survivors	
D6	Consume foods that contain soy (2 mg/day of isoflavone)

References:
<https://www.aicr.org/diet-activity-and-cancer/global-cancer-update-programme/cancer-survivors/>
<https://www.aicr.org/diet-activity-and-cancer/global-cancer-update-programme/cancer-survivors/breast-cancer-survivors-and-mortality-risk/>
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/14651621.bk-0073>
<https://www.aicr.org/health-advice-and-support/living-with-cancer/diet-well-during-cancer/can-i-eat-meat-if-i-have-or-have-had-cancer/>

B. Guidelines and Advice on Physical Activity for Breast Cancer Survivors

Guidelines	
PA1	150 - 300 min of MIAFA (moderate-intensity aerobic physical activity) OR at least 75-150 min VIFA (vigorous-intensity aerobic physical activity) per week
PA2	2 days per week muscle-strengthening
PA3	3 days per week balance and strength training
PA4	Limit sedentary time and replace it with physical activity of any intensity (including light intensity)

References:
<https://www.arhs.nl/newsroom/fact-sheets/detail/physical-activity>

C. Guidelines and Advice on Sleep for Breast Cancer Survivors

Guidelines	
S1	General guideline: Sleeping Well
S2	Sleep at least 7 hours a night
S3	Quality of sleep is also important
S4	A regular sleep pattern is crucial for achieving a restful and high-quality sleep

References:
<https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/survivors/healthy-living-guides/physical-health/sleep.htm>

D. Guidelines and Advice on Alcohol Use for Breast Cancer Survivors

Guidelines	
A1	Avoid or reduce alcohol intake (1 or less drinks per day)

References: <https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/alcohol/index.htm>

E. Guidelines and Advice on Tobacco Use for Breast Cancer Survivors

Guidelines	
T1	Avoid tobacco use

References:
<https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/survivors/health-care-providers/tobacco-use.htm>
https://cancercontrol.cancer.gov/ctoc/default/tiles/2022-07/Mon23_FactSheet_508.pdf

F. Guidelines and Advice on Anxiety and Distress for Breast Cancer Survivors

Guidelines	
AD1	Stress and anxiety can have a negative effect on breast cancer survivors' quality of life.
AD2	Anger can have a negative effect on breast cancer survivors' quality of life.
AD3	Loneliness can have a negative effect on breast cancer survivors' quality of life.

References:
<https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/survivors/healthy-living-guides/emotional-health/common-feelings.htm>

G. Rebecca-specific indicators for Breast Cancer Survivors

Rebecca specific indicators	
RSI1	Daily mobility
RSI2	Working after treatment
RSI3	Relationships and support systems
RSI4	Eating behaviours (eating rate and portions)

References:
<https://www.cancerivc.org.au/get-support/living-with-cancer/ife-after-treatment/living-well-after-cancer>
<https://www.cancerivc.org.au/downloads/resources/booklets/Living-Well-After-Cancer.pdf>
<https://www.cancerivc.org.au/get-support/cancer-services/service-types/sexuality-and-intimacy-service-type.html>
<https://www.cancerivc.org.au/get-support/work/cancer-and-work/cancer-work-and-you>

Figure 10. Example of the coded lifestyle recommendations included in the advisory guide.

The second part provided practical examples showing how HCPs could deliver advice based on the RWD collected (Figure 11). These examples included simple explanations and codes, allowing the HCP to easily record which aspects were discussed with the BCP at the end of each session.

Examples of advice	
<p>D3 + D1</p>	<p>Observation Based on your food log we/I notice that you consume fast foods quite often (can be specific times per week/month). It is important to reduce its intake as it tends to be high in unhealthy fats, starches, and sugars.</p> <p>Advice We/I would suggest when craving fast food, to opt for options like grilled chicken or fish, whole-grain buns, wraps, and plenty of vegetables. Ideally, if you have the time and the energy prepare homemade meals using fresh ingredients and lean proteins (e.g., avocado toast, pizza with whole grain wrap and fresh vegetables, etc) (D3). Besides reducing the fast food, it would be beneficial to try to increase the consumption of whole grains and legumes. These foods provide essential fiber, vitamins, minerals, and other nutrients that are crucial for the proper functioning of your body and there is evidence suggesting that fiber-rich foods may reduce the risk of mortality (D1). You can try including into your diet foods like oats, whole wheat bread, lentils, or beans daily. Some examples of how you can incorporate them into your meals are: a bowl of porridge with oats for breakfast, a lentil salad for lunch, and a whole grain avocado toast for dinner. You can also increase your legume consumption by adding them to soups, stews, wraps, or salads. When choosing whole grains and legumes, remember to check the fiber content on food labels and aim for approximately 25-30 grams of fiber per day (D1).</p>
<p>PA3</p>	<p>Observation Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I noticed you didn't perform any balance and strength training sessions last week.</p> <p>Advice We/I want to emphasize the importance of incorporating these sessions into your training routine. They play a key role in maintaining stability, supporting your joints, and reducing the risk of falls. How about trying one session this week? We can explore different options that suit your preferences and needs, such as yoga, tai chi, or specific balance training routines. These exercises can be enjoyable and beneficial for your physical health. As you progress, let's aim to gradually increase the number of sessions to three per week. This will help you build strength, improve balance, and enhance your overall stability. Remember, it's about finding a pace that works for you and fits into your lifestyle.</p>

Figure 11. Example of the advice included in the advisory guide.

Figure 12 Example of indicators visualised in the REBECCA dashboard.

All the relevant lifestyle indicators connected to the seven domains were monitored through the various data collection methods and visualised for the HCPs via the REBECCA dashboard (Figure 12).

Lifestyle and behavioural data were collected through multiple sources connected to the REBECCA system. Dietary patterns and alcohol consumption were assessed through meal and drink photos uploaded to the pApp. Physical activity and sleep were continuously monitored via the smartwatch, while tobacco use was reported through questionnaires. Emotional well-being, including anxiety and distress, was evaluated using questionnaires and complemented by smartwatch, companion's questionnaires and online activity data.

Daily mobility was captured through the smartwatch, which was Bluetooth-paired with the BCP's smartphone and the pApp. These devices locally recorded IMU data, including accelerometer and gyroscope signals, while the pApp logged geolocation (GPS) data from the phone. The pApp also maintained an internal usage log, which served as an indicator of compliance with the data collection protocol.

Work status after treatment could be inferred through a combination of questionnaire responses and mobility patterns, such as repeated daily visits to the same location for extended periods, suggesting a workplace. Eating rate was estimated through smartwatch data, while information about relationships and support systems was derived from the companion, internet history and mobility patterns (e.g., identifying individuals who rarely left their homes).

Together, these diverse data sources provided a comprehensive picture of each BCP's lifestyle and behaviour, forming the foundation for the REBECCA-assisted consultations. During these consultations, HCPs used the advisory guide alongside the RWD collected for each BCP. HCPs created a list with the coded lifestyle aspects warranted attention (e.g., D1, P3, AN1, S2) and engaged with patients to explore tailored strategies for improving these specific aspects of their life based on the examples in the guide. At the end of each consultation, the guide enabled HCP to clearly and efficiently document which recommendations had been discussed, supporting consistent reporting and comparability across clinical sites.

Conclusions

Deliverable D7.4 illustrates how multi-source RWD can be integrated into clinical workflows to enhance the management of BCPs. The REBECCA project applied a structured co-creation approach, engaging patients, HCPs, and researchers to ensure that digital tools and advisory resources were both clinically relevant and meaningful to patients.

The “Life Events” feature in the pApp enabled patients to report both positive and negative daily experiences, providing a more comprehensive view of their lives. Simultaneously, the unified advisory guide offered HCPs a standardized, evidence-based framework to deliver personalized lifestyle consultations, supporting consistent reporting and comparability across clinical sites.

Together, these tools demonstrate best practices for the use of patient-generated RWD in clinical care. They allowed HCPs to systematically interpret complex behavioural and lifestyle data, identify areas requiring intervention, and provide tailored recommendations, thereby improving patient-centred care.

The REBECCA methodology and outputs provide a scalable model for integrating RWD into healthcare practice, fostering evidence-based decision-making, enhancing post-cancer rehabilitation, and promoting the broader adoption of RWD in clinical research.

References

1. Global Cancer Observatory. <https://gco.iarc.fr/>
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10. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2024, August 26). *Sleeping Well* [Guide for cancer survivors]. <https://www.cdc.gov/cancer-survivors/healthy-living-guides/sleep.html>

ANNEX

A. ANNEX A: Advisory lifestyle guidelines

The guide is also available as a standalone document on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17425256>

Table of Contents

- A. Guidelines and Advice on **Diet** for Breast Cancer Survivors.....2
- B. Guidelines and Advice on **Physical Activity** for Breast Cancer Survivors6
- C. Guidelines and Advice on **Sleep** for Breast Cancer Survivors 11
- D. Guidelines and Advice on **Alcohol** Use for Breast Cancer Survivors 14
- E. Guidelines and Advice on **Tobacco** Use for Breast Cancer Survivors 16
- F. Guidelines and Advice on **Anxiety and Distress** for Breast Cancer Survivors 19
- G. **Rebecca-specific indicators** for Breast Cancer Survivors 23

A. Guidelines and Advice on Diet for Breast Cancer Survivors

Guidelines for cancer survivors	
D1	Increased intake of wholegrains and legumes
D2	Increased intake of vegetables and fruits
D3	Limitation of consumption of "fast food" and other processed foods high in fat, starch, or sugars
D4	Limitation of consumption of red meats (maximum 3 portions of 140g cooked red meat/week) and avoid processed meats
D5	Avoidance of sugary drink consumption
Limited evidence for breast cancer survivors	
D6	Consume foods that contain soy (2 mg/day of isoflavone)

References:

- <https://www.wcrf.org/diet-activity-and-cancer/global-cancer-update-programme/cancer-survivors/>
- <https://www.wcrf.org/diet-activity-and-cancer/global-cancer-update-programme/cancer-survivors/breast-cancer-survivors-and-mortality-risk/>
- <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/ijc.34321#jjc34321-bib-0075>
- <https://www.wcrf-uk.org/health-advice-and-support/living-with-cancer/eat-well-during-cancer/can-i-eat-meat-if-i-have-or-have-had-cancer/>

Examples of advice	
D3 + D1	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p><i>Based on your food log we/I notice that you consume fast foods quite often (can be specific times per week/month). It is important to reduce its intake as it tends to be high in unhealthy fats, starches, and sugars.</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p><i>We/I would suggest when craving fast food, to opt for options like grilled chicken or fish, whole-grain buns, wraps, and plenty of vegetables. Ideally, if you have the time and the energy prepare homemade meals using fresh ingredients and lean proteins (e.g., avocado toast, pizza with whole grain wrap and fresh vegetables, etc) (D3).</i></p> <p><i>Besides reducing the fast food, it would be beneficial to try to increase the consumption of whole grains and legumes. These foods provide essential fiber, vitamins, minerals, and other nutrients that are crucial for the proper functioning of your body and there is evidence suggesting that fiber-rich foods may reduce the risk of mortality (D1).</i></p> <p><i>You can try including into your diet foods like oats, whole wheat bread, lentils, or beans daily. Some examples of how you can incorporate them into your meals are: a bowl of porridge with oats for breakfast, a lentil salad for lunch, and a whole grain avocado toast for dinner. You can also increase your legume consumption by adding them to soups, stews, wraps, or salads. When choosing whole grains and legumes, remember to check the fiber content on food labels and aim for approximately 25-30 grams of fiber per day (D1).</i></p>

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D2	<p><u>Observation</u> <i>Based on your food log we/I see that your fruit and vegetable consumption is lower than the recommended (5 portions per day; the portioning can be avoided, as it is not something easy to identify)</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u> <i>Let's try to include more colourful vegetables and fruits into your meals. Some vegetables that you can add as a side in your main meals or in your salads, sandwiches, or wraps are broccoli, spinach, bell peppers, carrots, or sweet potatoes. Some fruits are berries, oranges, apples, bananas, or kiwis and can be enjoyed as snacks or added to your breakfast or salads.</i></p>
D3	<p><u>Observation</u> <i>Based on your food log we/I notice that you consume processed foods and sugary snacks frequently.</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u> <i>These foods are high in unhealthy additives, and it is recommended to limit their intake. Instead of processed snacks, you can choose nutritious alternatives like fresh or dried fruits (without sugar), raw nuts, Greek yogurt with berries, or homemade mix of nuts and dried fruits or root-fruits.</i></p>
D4 + D1	<p><u>Observation</u> <i>Based on your food log we/I see that you have red meat almost every day and you consume regularly processed meats such as bacon, ham, or salami during the week.</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u> <i>It would be beneficial to limit the red meat consumption (maximum 3 portions of 140g cooked red meat/week) and choose leaner protein sources like poultry (chicken or turkey), fish, or plant-based proteins (tofu, tempeh, Quorn or legumes) instead. To achieve that you can start by having smaller portions of red meat and try keeping some days meat-free (D4) (a feasible strategy might be to define specific meat-free days as the first step, E.g., introduce "Green-Tuesday")</i></p>

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	<p><i>Regarding process meats, there is no safe amount of consumption, and it is recommended to avoid them altogether, as they can be high in unhealthy additives and have been associated with adverse health effects, particularly for cancer survivors. You can replace processed meats with healthier protein sources such as hard-boiled eggs, grilled chicken or turkey breast, salmon, canned tuna in spring water, low-fat hummus, cream cheese or plant-based alternatives like seitan or tofu (D4).</i></p> <p><i>A good plant-based substitute of red meat are legumes (beans, lentils, chickpeas). A tip to increase their consumption is to add them to soups, stews, wraps, or salads. You can also make "legume balls" instead of meatballs with chickpeas (falafel), beans or lentils. When choosing legumes, remember to check the fiber content on food labels and aim for approximately 25-30 grams of fiber per day (D1).</i></p>
D5	<p><u>Observation</u> Your food log shows a significant intake of sugary drinks.</p> <p><u>Advice</u> It's important to be mindful of these beverages as they can lead to increased sugar consumption and potential health issues. It's best to opt for healthier drink options like water, herbal tea, or unsweetened beverages. Try water infused with fresh fruits like lemon, lime, or berries for a refreshing and flavourful twist! (one still debated point amongst nutritionists is the appropriateness of sugary-free substitutes of sugary drinks in nutritional advising – e.g., cola zero. We have no issues with this, and can also be considered. However, this might not be acceptable by the whole nutritional science domain and there might also be challenges for the general public to accept this)</p>
D6	<p><u>Advice</u> There is some limited evidence suggesting that consuming soy foods may have benefits for breast cancer survivors. Try including moderate amounts of soy foods in your diet, such as tofu, tempeh, edamame, and soy milk. Check the content of these foods in isoflavones from the food labels and aim for approximately 2mg/day of isoflavones from these sources.</p>

B. Guidelines and Advice on Physical Activity for Breast Cancer Survivors

	Guidelines
PA1	150 - 300 min of MIAPA (moderate-intensity aerobic physical activity) OR at least 75–150 min VIAPA (vigorous-intensity aerobic physical activity) per week
PA2	2 days per week muscle-strengthening
PA3	3 days per week balance and strength training
PA4	Limit sedentary time and replace it with physical activity of any intensity (including light intensity)

References:

<https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/physical-activity>

Examples of advice	
PA1	<p>Observation</p> <p>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I noticed you engaged in more than 100 min, moderate-intensity aerobic activity last week.</p> <p>Advice</p> <p>It's great! Let's aim to gradually increase it to 150 minutes. You can do that by engaging in activities like brisk walking, cycling, or swimming. (as a rule, the specific circumstances for each individual should be considered when providing this advice. Age, mobility and physical capabilities are important and should be considered. The living environment should also be taken in to consideration. One interventonal strategy can be to identify what type of aerobic exercise does the patient already do and try to increase the duration incrementaly).</p>
	<p>Observation</p> <p>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I see that you engaged in 60 minutes of vigorous-intensity aerobic activity last week.</p> <p>Advice</p> <p>Fantastic effort! Can we work towards reaching at least 75 minutes per week? Activities like running, dancing, or playing a sport (again, identify what is already present and built on that) that get your heart rate up can help you reach this goal. Do you need help to explore new options or overcome any challenges you might face?</p>

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PA2	<p>Observation</p> <p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I noticed you completed one muscle-strengthening session at the gym last week.</i></p> <p>Advice</p> <p><i>That's a good start! Research suggests doing these exercises twice a week for stronger bones, increased muscle mass, weight control and joint flexibility. If you do not enjoy weightlifting, you can incorporate into your training routine activities like resistance training or bodyweight exercises. Remember: exercises with elastic bands can be a good way to introduce such exercises for older individuals</i></p>
PA3	<p>Observation</p> <p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I noticed you didn't perform any balance and strength training sessions last week.</i></p> <p>Advice</p> <p><i>We/I want to emphasize the importance of incorporating these sessions into your training routine. They play a key role in maintaining stability, supporting your joints, and reducing the risk of falls. How about trying one session this week? We can explore different options that suit your preferences and needs, such as yoga, tai chi, or specific balance training routines. These exercises can be enjoyable and beneficial for your physical health. As you progress, let's aim to gradually increase the number of sessions to three per week. This will help you build strength, improve balance, and enhance your overall stability. Remember, it's about finding a pace that works for you and fits into your lifestyle.</i></p>
PA4	<p>Observation</p>

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	<p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I noticed there were long periods of sedentary time in your daily routine.</i></p> <p>Advice</p> <p><i>Let's aim to reduce this by replacing it with physical activity of any intensity every day. Even light-intensity movements, such as stretching, taking short walks, or doing household chores, can be beneficial. Remember, every step counts towards a healthier you! Introduction of very small walks at specific time of the day can be a good strategy here. E.g., identify usual time at home from the REBECCA dashboard and help the patient to introduce a small walk in the middle of the most pronounced sedentary period. In practice, conserving PA, this might be the main type of advice/intervention that REBECCA will support (and it is an important one!!!)</i></p>
<p>PA4 + RSI1&3</p>	<p>Observation</p> <p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I noticed that you spend long periods of time sitting and rarely leave your home.</i></p> <p>Advice:</p> <p><i>Let's try to change that and incorporate some physical activity into your daily routine. It doesn't have to be intense exercise. Even simple movements like stretching, short walks, or doing household chores can be helpful (PA4). Additionally, spending a lot of time at home can limit your social interactions, which are vital for your mental and emotional well-being. It is important to leave home and spend time out with your loved ones, engaging in activities that make you happy. It's not just about physical health but also your emotional well-being. Connecting with others and having a support system can make a positive difference in how you feel (RSI1 & 3).</i></p>

So, let's try to increase your physical activity and decrease the amount of time you spend at home. Take short walks in your neighbourhood and look for chances to go out and spend time with friends and family. It's all about finding a balance and taking care of yourself!

C. Guidelines and Advice on Sleep for Breast Cancer Survivors

	Guidelines
S1	General guideline: Sleeping Well
S2	Sleep at least 7 hours a night
S3	Quality of sleep is also important
S4	A regular sleep pattern is crucial for achieving a restful and high-quality sleep

References:

<https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/survivors/healthy-living-guides/physical-health/sleep.htm>

	Examples of advice
<p>S1+S2+ S3+S4</p>	<p>Observation: Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I noticed that: <i>You are struggling to get 7 hours of sleep every day/you are experiencing challenges in falling asleep (>30 min) / you are waking up multiple times during the night (more than once)/ it takes a while for you to fall back asleep after waking up (>20 min).</i></p> <p>Advice: Here are some tips that may help you:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To support your sleep, try to spend at least 15 minutes outdoors in the morning to soak up natural sunlight, which helps regulate your sleep hormone melatonin. 2. Establishing a consistent sleep routine is vital. Aim to go to bed and wake up at the same time every day, including weekends, to train your body's internal clock for better sleep. 3. Prioritize winding down before bedtime. Engage in relaxing activities like reading a book or taking a warm bath to calm your mind and prepare your body for a restful sleep. 4. Create an ideal sleep environment in your bedroom. Ensure it is quiet, dark, relaxing, and set at a comfortable temperature to promote a peaceful and uninterrupted night's sleep. 5. Improve your sleep hygiene by keeping electronic devices like TVs, computers, and smartphones out of the bedroom. This will reduce distractions and promote a more restful sleep. 6. To optimize your sleep, avoid consuming large meals, caffeine, and alcohol close to bedtime. Instead, opt for light, sleep-friendly snacks (e.g., banana, almond, yoghurt) and beverages (e.g., chamomile or valerian tea, warm milk) to support a more tranquil sleep. 7. Incorporating regular physical activity into your day can positively impact your sleep. Engage in moderate exercise, such as walking or yoga, to facilitate falling asleep more easily at night.

	<p>Observation</p> <p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard, we/I noticed that it takes you over an hour and a half to fall asleep each night, resulting in less than 7 hours of sleep. Furthermore, we/I observed from your online activity that you tend to spend too much time on your phone late at night, and the data from your wearable device indicates that you consume significant amounts of food before going to sleep.</i></p>
RSI4 + S2&3	<p>Advice</p> <p><i>We/I would recommend you make some lifestyle modifications that will improve your sleep and your overall health. First of all, eating a lot before bedtime can disrupt your sleep. When you eat a lot, especially late at night, your body must work on digesting the food instead of getting the rest it needs. This can make it harder for you to fall asleep and get the deep sleep you need. To help with this, we/I recommend having your last meal at least three hours before going to bed (RSI4). If you feel hungry later, go for light and sleep-friendly snacks like a banana, some almonds, or yogurt. You can also try sleep-promoting beverages like chamomile or valerian tea, or warm milk (S2&3). Lastly, using your phone before sleep does not help you relax and prepare for a good night's sleep. Therefore, try to keep all the electronic devices out of the room when going to sleep, and instead of using your mobile try reading a book or taking a warm bath (S2&3).</i></p>

D. Guidelines and Advice on Alcohol Use for Breast Cancer Survivors

	Guidelines
A1	Avoid or reduce alcohol intake (1 or less drinks per day).

References: <https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/alcohol/index.htm>

	Examples of advice
A1	<p><u>Observation</u> <i>Based on the pictures you have uploaded in the REBECCA app we/I noticed that you consume on average 5 alcoholic drinks per week.</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u> <i>Alcohol consumption can negatively affect your body's ability to heal and increases the chances of cancer recurrence. Additionally, it may interfere with your recovery, and it can also increase the risk of developing a new primary cancer. For these reasons it is advisable to limit (one drink or less in a day) or avoid alcohol consumption. Do you think you can reduce your alcohol consumption? Would you need help in finding ways to do it?</i></p>

	<p><i>Why Does Alcohol Use Raise Cancer Risk?</i></p> <p><i>When you drink alcohol, your body breaks it down into a chemical called acetaldehyde. Acetaldehyde damages your DNA and prevents your body from repairing the damage. DNA is the cell's "instruction manual" that controls a cell's normal growth and function. When DNA is damaged, a cell can begin growing out of control and create a cancer tumor.</i></p>

E. Guidelines and Advice on Tobacco Use for Breast Cancer Survivors

	Guidelines
T1	Avoid tobacco use

References:

<https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/survivors/health-care-providers/tobacco-use.htm>

https://cancercontrol.cancer.gov/sites/default/files/2022-07/Mon23_FactSheet_508.pdf

	Examples of advice
T1	<p>Observation</p> <p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard and the data from your wearable device we/I see that you continue smoking.</i></p> <p>Advice</p> <p><i>We/I understand that quitting smoking can be extremely challenging, but as a breast cancer survivor, it's important to recognize the significant benefits it brings to your health and well-being. Quitting smoking is one of the most effective ways to improve your chances of survival, enhance your quality of life, and maintain good overall health. Smoking weakens your immune system, leaving you more susceptible to infections. Additionally, studies indicate that breast cancer</i></p>

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	<p>survivors who smoke face a higher risk of mortality from cancer-related causes and have an increased risk of developing a new primary cancer. Quitting smoking greatly reduces this risk, enhances your response to breast cancer treatment and minimizes complications. Finally, it strengthens your body's natural defences, reduces the risk of severe infections, and improves your long-term survival. Do you think you can try quitting smoking? Would you need help in finding ways to do it?</p>
<p>T1 + A1 + RS11&3 + PA4</p>	<p>Observation:</p> <p>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard and the pictures uploaded in the REBECCA app, we/I noticed that you are smoking, consuming alcohol, and spending a significant amount of time at home lately.</p> <p>Advice:</p> <p>As a breast cancer survivor, it is necessary to prioritize your overall well-being and take steps to minimize any factors that may increase the risk of cancer recurrence or hinder your recovery. We/I would like to provide you with some advice regarding the concerns raised by your current lifestyle.</p> <p>First of all, smoking poses significant health risks and is associated with various types of cancer, including breast cancer. It is strongly recommended that you quit smoking to improve your health and reduce the likelihood of cancer recurrence. If you feel that you need help to do it, there are numerous resources available to support you in this journey, such as smoking cessation programs that I can recommend (T1).</p> <p>Secondly, alcohol consumption can have negative effects on your body's ability to heal and increase the chances of cancer recurrence. It may also interfere with your recovery process and increase the risk of developing new primary cancers. Try to avoid or limit your alcohol intake to one drink or less per day. I understand that reducing or eliminating alcohol may be challenging, but I think that it is worth making the effort (A1).</p> <p>Lastly, spending a lot of time at home limits your physical activity and may also limit your social interactions, which are essential for maintaining a healthy lifestyle. Regular exercise, (even small walks in your neighbourhood) can improve your physical and mental well-being, boost your immune system, and reduce the risk of cancer recurrence (PA4). Also, don't forget the importance of spending time with friends and family, engaging in activities that bring you joy, and connecting</p>

with others. Building strong social connections can provide you with emotional support, make you feel less alone, and have a positive impact on your well-being (RS1&3)!

You have already shown great strength in battling breast cancer, and I am sure you can make these lifestyle changes that will further enhance your health and well-being!

F. Guidelines and Advice on Anxiety and Distress for Breast Cancer Survivors

	Guidelines
AD1	Stress and anxiety can have a negative effect on breast cancer survivors' quality of life.
AD2	Anger can have a negative effect on breast cancer survivors' quality of life.
AD3	Loneliness can have a negative effect on breast cancer survivors' quality of life.

References:

<https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/survivors/healthy-living-guides/emotional-health/common-feelings.htm>

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	Examples of advice
AD1	<p><u>Observation</u> Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard and your online activity, we/I noticed that you've been dealing with a lot of stress lately.</p> <p><u>Advice</u> We/I want you to know that I'm here to provide guidance and support as we explore strategies together to help you find relief from the overwhelming stress you're facing. Some simple advice is:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. When you are feeling stressed, try going for a short walk or engaging in any form of exercise to help reduce tension and boost your mood. Introducing specific exercise sequences (e.g., easy to do yoga stances) for stress management can be a good idea. These should be short, as the goal is not PA increase, but rather stress management 2. Consider setting aside a few minutes each day for meditation or using relaxation apps/videos to help quiet your mind and promote a sense of calm. 3. Engaging in creative pursuits like painting, dancing, playing music, writing, or doing crafts can provide a therapeutic outlet and help you alleviate stress. The specific individual characteristics should be considered. 4. Connecting with fellow breast cancer survivors through support groups or online communities can offer an opportunity to share your feelings and gain insights from others who have experienced similar challenges. The different centers should make sure to have already identified such groups in each city/community. E.g., Amazonas for Stockholm.
AD2	<p><u>Observation</u> Based on what your companion has reported it seems that you are lately more angry than usual</p> <p><u>Advice</u></p>

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	<p><i>It's normal to feel angry after treatment for a lot of reasons. The diagnosis itself, a bad experience with a doctor, or an unsupportive friend or relative. These feelings may go away over time as you settle into your new routine. We/I want to share with you some tips that may help to alleviate your anger.</i></p> <p><i>First of all, it is important to ask yourself what's causing your anger and what you can do about it. Answering these questions and talking about how you're feeling can help you manage your anger. Another thing that can help, is to focus on what you can control. Being involved in your health care, keeping your appointments, making changes in your lifestyle, or even setting your daily schedule are things you can control. When you feel more in control, you're less likely to feel frustrated and angry. It is also effective to find ways to calm your temper. You can learn ways to redirect angry feelings and reframe your thoughts to alleviate anger and feel calmer. Finally, sometimes the best way to cope with anger is to join a cause. For example, becoming a cancer advocate could help give purpose and meaning to your experience.</i></p>
AD3	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard and the reports from the companion app, we/I have noticed that you have been showing signs of isolation and loneliness lately. It seems that you prefer to stay home, have not been joining the patient support meetings the last month and it has been a long time since you last met up with your friends.</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p><i>After treatment, it's easy to feel cut off from other people who may not understand what you're going through. And that's normal. You can consider joining support groups (in person or online) since it is a great way to meet with other survivors to share feelings, concerns, and journeys to a "new normal." Additionally, it would be helpful to have open conversations with your loved ones about your concerns, fears, and thoughts. Communicating your needs and concerns will not only make you feel better, but it will help them understand how you feel and help you.</i></p>
A1 + S4	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I notice that you consume a lot of alcohol particularly late at night and it takes you more than an hour to fall asleep every night. Considering this data, along with the content of your online activity, it seems like you have been experiencing high levels of stress lately.</i></p>

+	Advice
AD1	<i>We/I would recommend you make some lifestyle adjustments that will improve your overall mental and physical health and the effectiveness of your treatment. You can start by trying to decrease the alcohol consumption to one drink or less per day since it has a negative impact on your body's ability to recover and increases the chances of cancer recurrence (A1). It is also important to make an effort to go to bed and wake up at the same time every day, including weekends to be able to have a better sleep (S4). The quality of your sleep will improve, and you will feel less anxious if you engage in moderate intensity exercises like brisk walking, cycling, or calming activities like yoga and Pilates (PA1&3). To further reduce your anxiety, try practicing meditation for 5-15 minutes each day. Finally, to quiet your mind and foster a sense of calm you can try using relaxation apps or videos (AD1).</i>
+	
PA1&3	

Reference for physical activity (PA1&3):

Vijayvergia N, Denlinger CS. Lifestyle Factors in Cancer Survivorship: Where We Are and Where We Are Headed. J Pers Med. 2015 Jul 2;5(3):243-63. doi: 10.3390/jpm5030243. PMID: 26147495; PMCID: PMC4600146.

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G. Rebecca-specific indicators for Breast Cancer Survivors

	Rebecca specific indicators
RSI1	Daily mobility
RSI2	Working after treatment
RSI3	Relationships and support systems
RSI4	Eating behaviours (eating rate and portions)

References:

- <https://www.cancervic.org.au/get-support/living-with-cancer/life-after-treatment/living-well-after-cancer>
- <https://www.cancervic.org.au/downloads/resources/booklets/Living-Well-After-Cancer.pdf>
- <https://www.cancervic.org.au/get-support/cancer-services/service-types/sexuality-and-intimacy-service-type.html>
- <https://www.cancervic.org.au/get-support/work/cancer-and-work/cancer-work-and-you>

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Examples of advice	
RS11 + RS13	<p>Observation</p> <p>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard and the reports from the companion app, we/I have noticed that you have been showing signs of isolation and loneliness lately. It seems that you prefer to stay home, have not been joining the patient support meetings the last month and it has been a long time since you last met up with your friends.</p> <p>Advice</p> <p>We/I completely understand that what you are going through is not easy and you may feel that you want to be alone. And that's fine. We/I just want to remind you that spending time outside of home with your friends and family, engaging in activities that bring you joy, will make you feel better and have a positive impact on your overall well-being (RS11). We/I would encourage you to have open conversations with your partner about your concerns, fears, and thoughts. Communicating with your loved ones your needs and concerns will not only make you feel better, but it will help them understand how you feel and help you. Lastly, you can seek couples or family counselling, consult specialists or counsellors, or connect with support groups to navigate the changes and challenges you face and provide guidance and support (RS13).</p>
	<p>Observation</p> <p>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard, we/I have noticed that you have concerns about returning to work.</p> <p>Advice</p> <p>We/I understand that going back to work may seem difficult and stressful right now, but we/I would like to share with you some advice to make your transition back to work smoother. First of all, it is important to set realistic goals and not to put yourself undue pressure to perform at the same level as before your treatment. It would be helpful to have a gradual transition back to work and not to start working immediately full-time. You can start working part-time or with a modified</p>

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	<p>schedule to adjust to the new circumstances and monitor your energy levels and overall well-being. To keep your energy levels up, prioritize your self-care by planning breaks during the day, using stress-relieving methods, maintaining a balanced diet, exercising frequently, and making sure you receive enough sleep. You can also discuss with your employer about your treatment journey and your needs or any adjustments that can facilitate a smooth transition back to work. Finally, try creating a network of support in the workplace by discuss your experiences with co-workers or managers you can trust. This will create a supportive atmosphere and will help you feel less stress.</p>
RS14	<p>Observation</p> <p>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard, we/I have noticed that you tend to eat your meals quickly and consume large portions of food.</p> <p>Advice</p> <p>Eating fast and a lot, can lead to weight gain, indigestion and upset stomach, insulin resistance and other health problems. As a breast cancer survivor, it's important to maintain a healthy weight and adopt eating habits that can support your body's healing process.</p> <p>In order to eat your meals at a slower pace, try taking small bites and chew thoroughly. Take your time to enjoy the flavours and put your fork down between each bite. Aim to eat your meal for at least 20 minutes (or longer). Before eating, take a few deep breaths or perform a quick relaxation exercise. This can help you become more mindful of your hunger and satiety cues. Eat always sitting down in the table and avoid eating in front of the TV, scrolling on your phone, while driving or when you are stressed. Try to enjoy your food with family or friends whenever you can.</p> <p>In order to reduce the amount of food you consume without feeling deprived, serve your meals in smaller plates or bowls. Remember to start your meal with a salad or a serving of vegetables, to feel fuller and to prevent overeating during the main course. Another tip is to drink water before and during your meal because sometimes our bodies mistake thirst for</p>

REBECCA
Research on breast cancer induced chronic conditions
supported by causal analysis of multi-source data

hunger, leading to unnecessary eating. Finally, avoiding distractions as I already mention can help you being aware of the quantity of food you consume.

B. ANNEX B: Positive annotation categories

B.1 Initial list from brainstorming at KI

Enjoyed a meal
Met with a friend
Went out for a walk
Appreciated flowers/garden etc.
The weather was nice
Talked on the phone with friend/family
Could do something I could not do during treatment
Baked/cooked
Painted/sang/was creative
Read a good book
Listened to good music
Being able to take a walk/run
Being able to play with kids/grandchildren
Thankful for not experience pain (or other symptom)
Meet friends/family
A nice (unexpected) meeting/conversation with someone
Got a new friend/contact/relationship
Got in contact/meet with someone who he/she hasn't meet for a long time
Started a hobby that he/sha hasn't done for a while
Music
Doing or watching sports
Watching something (movie, series, show etc)
Reading a good book
Attending a concert/show/game/other event
The weather (sunny, snowy etc)
Being happy for someone else (who gave good news about something, for instance)
Enjoying a tasty meal/drink
Going to work
Producing/achieving something

Physical activity
I was able to do something, that wasn't possible when I was ill.
I exercised
Nutrition
I have cooked my favorite dish.
I went to a good restaurant.
Mindfulness
I did a relaxing activity.
I had a positive thought for my future.
Social interaction
I have received a compliment
I met a person, that I haven't met for a long time
Someone told me about his personal experience with a disease
Environment
I spent some time in the nature.
Small Victories:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trying/Completing things, I couldn't do yesterday/before. • Doing everyday things like cooking, shopping, having fika with friends/loved ones.
Life's Simple Pleasures:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enjoying the beauty of nature and the world around me. • Savouring the taste of my favourite foods/drinks. • Embracing the little moments that bring happiness and peace (reading a book, playing with my kid or pet, watching a movie, walking in the park etc.). • Enjoying the weather (sun, rain, rainbow etc.) / changing of seasons. • Enjoying a nice and relaxing sleep in a comfortable bed.
Supportive System/Relationships:
Feeling grateful for the support, encouragement and commitment to my well-being and recovery
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Family, friends, partners, kids, loved ones. • Cancer community. • Health care professionals.
Self-care, well-being, and mindfulness:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging in self-care activities (massage, body/facial treatments, yoga, meditation) • Taking time to enjoy and relax. • Finding peace of mind and forgiving

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning something new.
Acts of kindness:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Random acts of kindness from strangers to me, and vice versa. • Inspiring hope in others facing similar challenges. • Helping someone who is in need. • Sending or receiving a card to/from a friend that lives far. • Buying/receiving a present.
Celebrations/Shared moments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Birthdays, anniversaries, parties. • Cherishing moments of laughter, love, and connection. • Planning a trip with me loved ones or by myself.
Inner Strength:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being proud of my resilience and determination to fight through challenging times. • Appreciating and being grateful for each day. • Accepting my healing process, being patient and kind to myself.
I achieved something I could not before.
I had more energy than earlier.
I spent time with family.
I saw something beautiful.
I appreciated something about my day.
Someone did something kind to me.
I did something kind to another person.
I felt joy.
I was pain- free.
I did something creative.
I laughed a lot.
Self-care, physical:
I got out of bed as planned
I did a morning stretch
I took a morning walk
I had a nice breakfast
I had a healthy breakfast
I showered and washed my hair
I washed and styled my hair

I treated myself to a haircut
I moisturized with my favorite bodylotion
I did a manicure/I treated myself to a manicure
I did a pedicure/I treated myself to a pedicure
I had a massage/I treated myself to a massage
I wore a nice outfit
I treated myself to a new outfit
I cleaned out and organized my wardrobe/other space
I listened to good music
I had a lovely meal
I tried something new
I tried something I've always wanted to try
I learnt something new
I learnt something I've always wanted to learn
Self care, social/relationships:
I smiled at people on the street when running errands
A stranger smiled at me today when running errands
I had a nice chat with my neighbour/cashier/postman/other
I had a nice chat with a friend/relative
I had coffee with a friend/relative
I took a walk with a friend/relative
I joined a bookclub
I joined a dance class/any other type of class
I went to the gym/exercised with a friend/relative
I went to a museum/exhibition/art gallery/theatre/concert with a friend/relative
I planned a trip with a friend
I booked a trip with a friend
I visited a friend/relative over the day/weekend
Self-care, mental:
I smiled at my reflection
I did not criticize myself
I said positive affirmations
I was present in the moment
I felt present in the moment

B.2 List after grouping the events into categories

	Examples
Small Victories	<p>Could do something I could not do during treatment / when I was ill</p> <p>I was able to do something, that I could not do yesterday</p> <p>I achieved something I could not before.</p> <p>I was pain-free</p> <p>Being able to take a walk/run</p> <p>Being able to play with kids/grandchildren</p> <p>I had more energy than earlier</p> <p>I got out of bed as planned</p> <p>I quit smoking/ I did not smoke today</p> <p>I stopped drinking/ I did not drink alcohol today</p> <p>Producing/achieving something</p> <p>Going to work</p>
Enjoying Life's Simple Things	<p>The weather was nice</p> <p>The weather (sunny, snowy etc) / changing of seasons</p> <p>Appreciated flowers/garden etc</p> <p>I spent some time in the nature</p> <p>Environment</p> <p>I saw something beautiful</p> <p>Enjoying a tasty meal/drink</p> <p>I had a nice/tasty breakfast</p> <p>I have cooked my favorit dish / I had a lovely meal</p> <p>I went to a good restaurant</p> <p>Baked/cooked</p> <p>Read a good book</p> <p>Listened to good music</p> <p>Attending a concert/show/game/other event</p> <p>Watching something (movie, series, show etc)</p> <p>Painted/sang/was creative</p> <p>Enjoying a nice and relaxing sleep in a comfortable bed</p> <p>I did a relaxing activity</p> <p>I played with my pet</p> <p>I hugged someone that I love</p> <p>I laughed a lot</p> <p>I felt joy</p> <p>Doing or watching sports</p> <p>Went out for a walk</p> <p>I excersiced</p>

Social interaction	<p>Meet friends/family</p> <p>Talked on the phone with friend/family</p> <p>I spent time with family</p> <p>I had a nice chat/coffe/walk with a friend/relative</p> <p>I went to the gym/exercised with a friend/relative</p> <p>I went to a museum/exhibition/art gallery/theatre/concert with a friend/relative</p> <p>I visited a friend/relative over the day/weekend</p> <p>A nice (unexpected) meeting/conversation with someone</p> <p>I met a person, that I haven't met for a long time</p> <p>Got in contact/meet with someone who he/she hasn't meet for a long time</p>
Supportive System	<p>Someone told me about his personal experience with a disease</p> <p>I felt the support of my family, friends, partners, kids, loved ones</p> <p>I felt the support of my health care professionals</p> <p>I felt the support of the cancer community I am in</p> <p>I had an interesting discussion that invigorated/inspired me</p>
Celebrations/Shared moments	<p>I celbrated my birthday</p> <p>I celbrated my anniversary with my partner</p> <p>I celbrated a year cancer-free</p> <p>I was at my granddaughters's birthday party</p> <p>I planned/booked a trip</p> <p>Being happy for someone else (who gave good news about something, for instance)</p> <p>I had a deep conversation with a friend/relative</p> <p>I was with my daughter when she gave birth</p> <p>I / a colleague retired today and we had a goodbye party with my colleagues</p>
New Experiences/Hobbies	<p>I tried something new</p> <p>I tried something I've always wanted to try</p> <p>I learnt something new</p> <p>I learnt something I've always wanted to learn</p> <p>Started a hobby that he/sha hasn't done for a while</p> <p>Got a new friend/contact/relationship</p> <p>I joined a bookclub</p> <p>I joined a dance class/any other type of class</p> <p>I visited a place I've never been before</p>

Acts of kindness	<p>I have received a compliment I complimented a stranger I complimented a friend/relative Helping someone who is in need I took care of an injured animal Inspiring hope in others facing similar challenges. Sending or receiving a card to/from a friend that lives far. Buying/receiving a present. Someone did something kind to me. I did something kind to another person. I smiled at people on the street when running errands A stranger smiled at me today when running errands I had a nice chat with my neighbour/cashier/postman/other</p>
Self-care, well-being, and mindfulness	<p>I started the morning with a guided meditation/body scan/routine that helps my body and mind to be calm I had a healthy breakfast I showered and washed my hair / styled my hair I treated myself to a haircut I moisturized with my favorite bodylotion I did a manicure/pedicure/I treated myself to a manicure I had a massage/I treated myself to a massage I wore a nice outfit / I treated myself to a new outfit I cleaned out and organized my wardrobe/other space I smiled at my reflection I did not criticize myself / others I said positive affirmations I was/felt present in the moment I had positive thoughts about myself I meditated / did yoga / I practised taking some deep breaths / Mindfulness I cleared my mind, and thought of nothing I reflected on past events without feeling anxiety/sadness/anger I appreciated something about my day I had a positive thought about my future I am proud of my resilience and determination to fight through challenging times I appreciate and I am grateful for each day I accept my healing process, I am patient and kind to myself Thankful for not experience pain (or other symptom)</p>

B.3 Meetings minutes and final list

B.3.1 Minutes from Amazonas meetings

2023-10-09

Participants:

- Britt Sandberg
- Ewa Ellis
- Linda Engström
- Matilda Ersson
- Rahma Wehelie
- Roelinde Middelveld
- Vasileios Papapanagiotou (första kvarten)

Positive events

- Britt and Linda participated in a meeting on 9/10 with Alkyoni Glympi (KI), Ioannis Ioakeimidis (KI), Ioannis Sarafis (AUTH), and Vasileios Papapanagiotou (AUTH) regarding the reporting of positive events and how this can be implemented in the app.
- From the developers' side, this can be done within the existing timeframe, and the plan is to integrate it in the next version of the app.
- Ioannis S. has checked with the clinical sites, who have agreed to allow the app's appearance to be changed during the ongoing study.
- For the user, the flow will be as follows: choose to take a photo, click on "life events" (or similar), select "positive" or "negative" (possibly other wording), take a photo, with the option to make notes in free text.
- Next steps: Alkyoni will summarize the material in English, Amazona will adjust/approve, and a post will be made in Teamwork with a request for INCLIVA and SUH to provide feedback.

2023-09-11

Participants:

- Anita Wanngren
- Britt Sandberg
- Linda Engström
- Rahma Wehelie
- Alkyoni Glympi
- Clara Schidelko

“Positive events”

- Alkyoni reports that the research group at KI has followed up on the input provided by participants during the spring test, indicating that they want the ability to report positive events/daily occurrences and not just focus on negative health aspects, stressors, etc. Ten women in the research group were invited to participate in brainstorming about what could be positive events in daily life for breast cancer survivors. Six women shared their thoughts and ideas. The challenge now is to figure out how these events should be categorized and implemented in the mobile app (pApp).
- We discussed that the fact that many breast cancer survivors continue to work to a greater or lesser extent is an important factor to include, as well as different aspects of being outdoors, e.g., being in the garden or experiencing nature with all senses. At the same time, it is not certain that all individuals perceive the same things as positive or negative; for example, a phone call from a relative or friend may be perceived as positive for one person but negative for another. One suggestion is therefore to make such mapping on an individual level, i.e., what is perceived as positive/energizing and negative/draining.
- Different ways of sharing data about positive events and using the data were discussed: categorizing an event, taking a photo, writing a comment; the possibility of using reminder functionality for positive events; registering if an individual reports more negative than positive events.
- As a next step, Alkyoni will contact the developers to check if there are any technical limitations to consider and how this could be implemented.

2023-09-25

Participants:

- Anita Wanngren
- Britt Sandberg
- Linda Engström
- Matilda Ersson
- Roelinde Middelveld

“Positive events”

- Britt presented a compilation of proposed categories for positive events, and a few updates were made.
- The group agreed that “Stressors” and “Positive events” should contain the same categories, as a category classified as positive for one person may be classified as negative for another. The same person may also classify a category differently at different times.
- Linda will relay the above to Alkyoni and mentioned that we would like to conduct a poll/vote among our members to see which categories are perceived as most relevant to use.

B.3.2 Final categories for the “life events” in the REBECCA app (pApp)

Positive event categories	Negative event categories
Social contacts	Social contacts
Partner/Family	Partner/Family
Pets	Pets
Food and drinks	Food and drinks
Home and Household	Home and Household
Nature/Environment	Nature/Environment
Work and other occupations	Work and other occupations
Transport/Travel	Transport/Travel
Health/Wellness/Beauty	Health
Exercise and Physical Activity	Exercise and Physical Activity
Culture/Amusement/Hobby	Culture/Amusement/Hobby
Society/Regulations	Society/Regulations
Other	Safety and security
	Other